

IoT- Based Smart Crop Health Monitoring System Using Machine Learning

Abdul. Azeem | A. Priyanka | B. Revathi | CH.Sai Vinitha

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Andhra Loyola Institute of Engineering and Technology, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh, India

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KEYWORDS

IoT, crop health monitoring, DHT11 sensor, Soil moisture Sensor ,rain and light intensity Sensor, machine learning, Raspberry Pi, precision agriculture, thingspeak.

ABSTRACT

Agricultural productivity depends on various environmental factors, making real-time monitoring of soil and atmospheric conditions crucial for crop health assessment. This paper presents an IoT-based Smart Crop Health Monitoring System utilizing Raspberry Pi and multiple sensors to determine whether a crop is healthy or not. The system integrates a moisture sensor, DHT11 sensor (for temperature and humidity), rain sensor and a light intensity sensor to monitor key environmental parameters affecting plant growth. The collected sensor data is processed on Raspberry Pi and stored both on an SD card for local logging and in Thingspeak an IoT cloud platform, for remote monitoring and analysis. To enhance decision-making, machine learning algorithms analyze the sensor data, predicting crop health status based on environmental conditions. If abnormalities such as low soil moisture, extreme temperatures, or insufficient sunlight are detected, the system provides real-time alerts and recommendations for corrective actions. This IoT-enabled precision farming solution allows farmers to remotely access crop health data via Thingspeak, ensuring timely intervention, resource optimization, and sustainable agricultural practices. By leveraging machine learning for predictive analysis, the system enhances crop productivity, minimizes manual monitoring efforts, and promotes smart farming techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of the global population and the increasing demand for food have necessitated innovative approaches to agriculture. Traditional farming practices

often lead to inefficient resource use and suboptimal crop yields. The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and machine learning offers a sustainable solution to these challenges.

This paper proposes a smart crop health monitoring system that leverages IoT technology and machine learning to automate irrigation, monitor environmental conditions, and provide actionable insights for farmers, which is time-consuming and inefficient. With advancements in IoT and machine learning, automated crop health monitoring has become a feasible and effective solution.

1.1. Objectives:

1. To Design and implement a smart crop health monitoring system that integrates various environmental sensors (soil moisture, temperature, humidity, rainfall, and light intensity) with a Raspberry Pi for real-time data collection and analysis.
2. To Create an automated irrigation system that activates based on soil moisture levels, ensuring optimal water usage and reducing wastage.
3. To Collect and analyze environmental data using machine learning algorithms to predict crop health and identify potential diseases based on sensor readings.
4. To Develop a crop recommendation feature that utilizes NPK values and sensor data to suggest suitable crop for cultivation, enhancing agricultural productivity.

1.2. Principles of crop health:

- **Soil Health:** Healthy crops require a balanced supply of essential nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, etc.) from the soil. Soil health is influenced by its composition, structure, and microbial activity.
- **Water management:** Regular monitoring of soil moisture levels helps in making informed irrigation decisions, ensuring that crops receive the right amount of water.
- **Climate Factors:** Temperature, humidity, and light levels significantly impact crop growth and health. Understanding local climate conditions helps in selecting suitable crop varieties and management practices.

2. RELATED WORK

Farmers often rely on visual inspections and manual data collection, which can be time-consuming and prone to human error. This approach lacks real-time data and can lead to delayed responses to crop health issues. Regular soil testing is conducted to assess nutrient levels, but it requires laboratory analysis and can be infrequent, leading to outdated information. Basic data collection methods do not utilize advanced analytics or machine

learning, resulting in missed opportunities for predictive insights and proactive management.

2.1 Existing IoT Solutions:

Fragmented Systems: Many IoT-based solutions exist, but they often operate in silos, lacking interoperability. This fragmentation can lead to inefficiencies and increased complexity for farmers trying to manage multiple systems.

High Costs: Some existing can be expensive to implement and maintain, making them less accessible for small-scale farmers.

Basic Functionality: While some mobile apps provide monitoring capabilities, they often lack comprehensive features such as real-time alerts, predictive analytics, and integration with other agricultural tools.

3. PROPOSED APPROACH

A. RASPBERRY PI:

The Raspberry Pi 3B+ is a versatile single-board computer widely used in various applications. Acts as the central processing unit for collecting and processing sensor data. Interface with multiple sensors (soil moisture, DHT11, rain, light intensity). Connects to the cloud platform for data transmission.

B. SOIL MOISTURE SENSOR:

The soil's moisture content is detected using the Soil Moisture sensor. It measures the amount of moisture or water content in the soil. Coefficients are used in the soil moisture sensor to perform computations. It calculates the amount of water that is present in the soil. It obtains and transmits analog signals that are displayed digitally, as well as detecting the amount of water in the soil. It sends signals to raspberry pi for additional processing and display that comprise information, data, or values related to the state of the soil.

C. DHT11 SENSOR:

Although the DHT11 and DHT22 sensors are slow and rudimentary, they are excellent for enthusiasts who wish to perform some simple data logging. The capacitive humidity sensor and the temperature are the two components that make up the DHT sensors.

- **Power Supply:** Operates on a voltage range of 3 to 5V, making it compatible with the Raspberry Pi's GPIO pins.
- **Current Consumption:** Uses a maximum current of 2.5mA during data conversion (when requesting data).

- **Temperature Range:** Capable of measuring temperatures between 0 and 50°C with an accuracy of ±2°C.
- **Humidity Range:** Measures humidity levels between 20 and 80% with an accuracy of ±5%.
- **Physical Dimensions:** Compact size of 15.5 x 12 x 5.5 mm, allowing for easy integration.

D. LIGHT SENSOR:

Light sensors operate via the photoelectric effect. Light may act like a particle, known as a photon. When a photon strikes the metal surface of the light sensor, its energy is absorbed by the electrons, increasing their kinetic energy and allowing them to be ejected from the material.

Dual technology, which is commonly used in security systems and outdoor lighting to respond to both humans and things such as automobiles, employs a combination of passive infrared and microwave sensors to detect moving objects and trigger a response.

- If value is <500 exposed under sunshine
- If value is 100 to 500 lightening is good
- If value is <100 – evening

E. RAIN SENSOR:

A rain sensor is a device that detects rainfall and activates or deactivates systems like irrigation accordingly. It typically works by measuring changes in moisture or light reflection, allowing it to respond to rain and prevent unnecessary operation during wet conditions.

Rain sensors utilize various technologies to detect moisture. Common methods include:

F. MOTOR DRIVER:

Motor driver (L298N 2A) controls the operation of pumps and motors that irrigate crops. when soil moisture level drops below threshold value the motor driver activates the irrigation system to deliver the water to the plants.

This automation ensures that crops receive the right amount of water at the right time, reducing water wastage and improving crop health.

- If $S1 < 25$ it activates the water pump.
- If $S1 \geq 25$ it deactivates the water pump.

G. LCD DISPLAY:

The LCD Displays current readings from various sensors, allowing users to monitor environmental

conditions at a glance. Easily integrated into the system setup, making it suitable for field use.

Provides a summary of crop health based on sensor data (e.g., if Crop Health is Good then it shows: normal condition, If crop health is not good then it shows: Not Good)

Fig 1: Block Diagram

3.1 LEAF DISEASE IDENTIFICATION:

Leaf disease identification using machine learning in IoT-based systems enhances crop health monitoring by enabling real-time disease detection and management. Various studies highlight the integration of machine learning algorithms with IoT technologies to accurately identify plant diseases, improving agricultural productivity and sustainability.

Leaf diseases can significantly reduce crop yields and quality. Early detection is crucial for effective management and minimizing losses. The system utilizes a combination of sensors and cameras connected to a Raspberry Pi to monitor crop health.

- **Real-time Analysis:** Machine learning models can analyze images of leaves in real-time, providing immediate feedback on plant health.
- **High Accuracy:** Advanced algorithms can achieve high accuracy in identifying various diseases, reducing the chances of misdiagnosis.

3.2 Machine learning algorithms used:

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):

Particularly effective for image classification tasks, CNNs can learn features from leaf images to identify diseases.

Support Vector Machines (SVM):

SVMs can classify leaf images based on extracted features, providing a robust method for disease detection.

	Bell Pepper	Potato	Tomato
Healthy			
Disease	 Tomato Mosaic Virus		

Fig 2: Healthy leaves vs Disease leaves

By uploading the leaf image it will predict the type of disease. Based on the identified disease, the system provides actionable recommendations, such as specific treatments, fungicides, or cultural practices to mitigate the disease. Here in the result, it will display the crop name and name of the disease it also shows the cause of disease and how to cure or prevent it.

So, By enabling early detection and informed decision-making, this system enhances crop health management, optimizes resource use, and promotes sustainable agricultural practices.

3.3 CROP RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM:

The crop recommendation system using IoT and machine learning integrates real-time data from sensors monitoring soil and environmental conditions with machine learning algorithms to analyze this data. By evaluating factors such as soil nutrients, moisture levels, and climate, the system provides tailored crop suggestions to optimize yield and resource use for farmers.

Selecting the right crop for specific environmental conditions can significantly enhance yield and quality. Proper crop selection minimizes resource wastage (water, fertilizers, pesticides) and maximizes productivity. The crop recommendation system utilizes data collected from various sensors (soil moisture, temperature, humidity, light intensity) connected to a Raspberry Pi. Continuous monitoring of environmental parameters provides real-time insights into the conditions affecting crop growth.

Fig 3: Evaluating factors for right crop

Users can view information about each recommended crop, including:

- **Growth Requirements:** Ideal soil conditions, moisture levels, and temperature ranges.
- **Expected crop:** Potential crop estimates based on current conditions.
- **Pest and Disease Resistance:** Information on the crop's resistance to common pests and diseases.

4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

Data collection: Sensors deployed in the field continuously monitor environmental parameters such as soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and nutrient levels. This data is transmitted to a central processing unit.

Real-Time Analysis: The collected data is analyzed using algorithms to assess crop health and detect any anomalies. This analysis helps in identifying potential issues like nutrient deficiencies or water stress.

Leaf Disease Identification: The images of crops are captured or uploaded. These images are processed with machine learning algorithms trained to recognize symptoms of various leaf diseases. The system diagnoses potential diseases and suggests management strategies.

Crop Recommendation System: The insights from crop health monitoring and disease identification are integrated. An algorithm evaluates the data to recommend suitable crops based on current environmental conditions, soil health, and disease status, optimizing planting decisions.

5.WORK FLOW

Sensors are installed in the fields to gather data on environmental conditions. The temperature, humidity, and soil moisture sensors provide digital and analog data to the controller, which processes it and essentially produces three outputs. Temperature and moisture readings are shown on the LCD device.

The sensors send real-time data to a cloud-based platform or local server for processing. The system analyzes the incoming data to monitor crop health and identify any diseases. Images of crops are analyzed using

machine learning to detect diseases. Based on the analysis, the system generates alerts for farmers and provides crop recommendations to optimize yield and resources. Farmers receive alerts and recommendations via mobile apps or dashboards, allowing them to take timely actions to improve crop health and productivity.

6.CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The connections diagram are the sensors are connected to each other for sensing. This temperature and humidity sensor connects to the Raspberry Pi's GPIO pins, allowing it to read environmental data. The rain sensor Typically connected to a GPIO pin, it detects rainfall and can trigger actions like activating a motor or sending alerts.

This sensor measures soil moisture levels and can be connected to the Raspberry Pi via analog-to-digital converters like the MCP3208, enabling data processing.

The Light Sensor Often a photoresistor or similar device, it connects to the GPIO pins to monitor light levels, which can inform irrigation or lighting systems.

Fig 4. Executed circuit with connections

Motor Driver is component interfaces with the Raspberry Pi to control motors based on sensor inputs, allowing for automated actions like opening or closing irrigation valves. The Dc motor is connected to storing of water. The motor is on when the land is dry. It stops pumping when the land is wet. MCP3208 An analog-to-digital converter that allows the Raspberry Pi to read analog signals from sensors like soil moisture sensor, enabling precise data collection and analysis.

This time, we're linking it to the Thing Speak website (https://thingspeak.com/pages/learn_more). With the help of the cloud-based analytics platform service Thing Speak TM, you can gather, view, and evaluate real-time data streams. Data uploaded by your devices to Thingspeak is instantly visualized by Thing speak.

5.RESULTS

Fig 5: Output value of Temperature

Fig 6: Output values of soil moisture

second fig explains the moisture value, first fig explains the temperature value. Starting to last the moisture is same due the land is dry. The temperature is

changed from 33 to 34. Then slightly changes based on atmospheric conditions.

Fig 7: Output values of humidity

Fig 8: Output values of Light

Based upon their external inputs the values is changed using sensors we can take inputs and analyse it then the output values is plotted using plot .the first plot shows the humidity value is starting is high 40.6 then it reduced then it changes to 40.5. The light intensity is starting is 41 then it changes to high then slightly changes to low.

Fig 9: Output values of rain sensor

Fig 10: Result of leaf disease identification

By uploading leaf image to it ,it will predict and display crop name ,disease,cause of the disease and how to prevent it.

Fig 11: Crop recommendation with suggestions

By evaluating the factors like sensors data and npk values it will recommend best crop and suggestions that farmers can work upon.

6.CONCLUSION

In modern agriculture, the integration of technology and data-driven approaches is essential for optimizing crop health and productivity. A comprehensive system that includes crop health monitoring, leaf disease identification, and crop recommendation can significantly enhance farming practices. By utilizing sensors such as the DHT11 for temperature and humidity, rain sensors, soil moisture sensors, and light sensors, farmers can gather real-time data on environmental conditions. This data is processed using machine learning algorithms to identify potential diseases in crops and recommend suitable crops based on current soil and climate conditions. The use of a Raspberry Pi as the central processing unit, along with components like the MCP3208 for analog-to-digital conversion and motor drivers for automated irrigation, creates a robust framework for smart agriculture. The principles of crop health emphasize the importance of soil health, water management, pest and disease control,

crop diversity, and environmental conditions in achieving optimal agricultural outcomes. By evaluating these factors and leveraging technology, farmers can make informed decisions that lead to increased yields, reduced resource waste, and sustainable farming practices. The implementation of an IoT-based crop health monitoring system not only enhances productivity but also promotes environmental stewardship, ensuring that agricultural practices are sustainable for future generations. As technology continues to evolve, the potential for improving crop health and agricultural efficiency will only grow, paving the way for a more resilient and productive agricultural sector.

7. FUTURE WORK

For the future work, the role of other parameters related to crop health will be investigated, which may enhance the performance of the proposed work. Additionally, the soil properties using Sensor data and their effect on crop health will be analyzed.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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